

Elevated Temperature Internal Friction Due to Composite Structure in Sintered Silicon Nitrides

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ABSTRACT

The elastic stiffness and internal friction of hot-press sintered (HPS) and pressureless sintered (PLS) silicon nitrides at elevated temperatures were measured in 10 MHz range with the ultrasonic pulse method and in 1 Hz range with the torsion pendulum method. The results were analyzed taking account of the composite structure composed of silicon nitride grains and a grain boundary phase deriving from the sintering additives. The values of the activation energy of the viscosity of the grain boundary phase obtained for HPS ($\text{Si}_3\text{N}_4\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-Y}_2\text{O}_3$), PLS ($\text{Si}_3\text{N}_4\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-Y}_2\text{O}_3$), PLS ($\text{Si}_3\text{N}_4\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-MgO}$) and PLS ($\text{Si}_3\text{N}_4\text{-SrO-MgO-CeO}_2$) were 218, 203, 159 and 149 kcal/mol, respectively. Measurements were made also for a reaction sintered material which has in principle no grain boundary phase.

INTRODUCTION

Silicon nitride is one of the covalent crystal ceramics and has excellent chemical and physical stabilities at elevated temperatures. Because of the above stabilities, however, it is difficult to sinter it in the pure state, and usually some oxides are used as additives to promote sintering. The sintered materials, therefore, have a composite structure composed of silicon nitride grains and a grain boundary phase which derives from the additives. This phase is usually amorphous, and at elevated temperatures its viscous behavior exerts considerable effects upon the mechanical properties of the sintered materials. In order to obtain information on the viscous properties of the grain boundary phase at elevated temperatures, the internal friction method has been often used (1-3), which was originally used by Kê (4) to investigate the stress relaxation due to grain boundary viscosity in polycrystalline metals. In Ref.(3), the present authors tried measurements of the internal friction in 10 MHz range with the ultrasonic pulse method and in 1 Hz range with the inverted torsion pendulum method. In this paper, newly obtained data are added and the viscous properties of the grain boundary phase are discussed.

EXPERIMENTAL

Tested Materials

Measurements were made for the sintered silicon nitrides shown in Table I. Besides the hot-press sintered and pressureless sintered materials, a reaction

sintered one which would have in principle no grain boundary phase was tested for the sake of comparison. In the following description, the abbreviations given in the third column of the table are used.

Table I Tested Materials

<u>Sintering method</u>	<u>Additives</u>	<u>Abbreviations</u>
hot-press sintered	Al ₂ O ₃ -Y ₂ O ₃	HPS
pressureless sintered	Al ₂ O ₃ -Y ₂ O ₃	PLS-1
	Al ₂ O ₃ -MgO	PLS-2
	SrO-MgO-CeO ₂	PLS-3
reaction sintered		RS

Ultrasonic Measurements

By measuring the propagation velocity and attenuation of the ultrasonic pulse, the elastic stiffness and internal friction of the specimen can be determined, respectively. In order to avoid the difficulty in using the couplant between the buffer rod and the specimen at elevated temperatures, which is an inherent difficulty in the buffer rod method, the differential path method (5) shown in Fig.1 was adopted (3). Long specimens were used which had a sharp cut near to the free end. The time separation between the echo pulses from the cut and from the free end gives the velocity of the ultrasonic pulse in the test section (from the cut to the free end) where the temperature distribution is expected to be uniform, and the change in the ratio of the heights of these two echo pulses gives the change in the attenuation caused by elevating temperature. In the above method there are two difficulties (3). Firstly, the measurement is limited to a low attenuation range, since the increase in the attenuation due to the rise of temperature occurs not only in the test section but also in the wave guide section (from the transducer to the cut) positioned in the furnace. Secondly, the echo pulse from the free end often overlaps with the trailing pulses of the echo pulse from the cut. This often makes the measurement difficult. By using the shear wave, the results shown in Fig.2 were obtained. The longitudinal wave gave almost similar results.

Torsion Pendulum Measurements

Measurements in 1 Hz range were made with a standard inverted torsion pendulum apparatus (3). The frequency and decay rate of the free oscillation give respectively the elastic stiffness and internal friction. An infrared image furnace is used for heating the specimen. Two types of specimens shown in Fig.3 were used. Since the grip ends of the specimen are outside the furnace, in case of the type 1 specimen a correction is made for data by assuming that the changes in the elastic stiffness and internal friction caused by elevating temperature occur only in the central part 55 mm in length. In order to avoid the application of such a correction, in the type 2 specimen, the length of the parallel part is limited to 55 mm. The cross section of the parallel part is a circle 3 mm in diameter or a square 3 mm or 2.8 mm in side length. The strain amplitude dependences of the dynamic elastic stiffness and internal friction were tested using a HPS specimen over a twisting angle amplitude range 1×10^{-5} to 2×10^{-4} rad/mm, and it was confirmed that the amplitude dependences were not observed even at elevated temperatures. Measurements were conducted at twisting angle amplitudes around 5×10^{-5} rad/mm, which is in the above range. The results are shown in Fig.4.

DISCUSSION

Ultrasonic and Torsion Pendulum Data

Figures 2 and 4 show a general tendency that the elastic stiffness decreases and the internal friction increases at elevated temperatures. The internal friction begins to rise abruptly at a temperature. As is seen in the results of the torsion pendulum measurements shown in Fig.4, the internal friction at elevated temperatures is composed of a component which forms a peak and a background component which rises monotonously with temperature. Corresponding to the peak of the internal friction, a steep fall of the elastic stiffness is also observed. On the other hand, as is shown in Fig.2, the ultrasonic measurements were limited to the beginning part of the rise of the internal friction. This is due to the

limitation in the measurement already described in the subsection "Ultrasonic Measurements".

The peak and background components of the internal friction observed in the sintered silicon nitrides have been interpreted respectively in terms of the stress relaxation due to the viscous flow of the grain boundary phase and the internal friction in the silicon nitride grains (1) on the basis of Kê's grain boundary relaxation model of the polycrystalline metals (4).

Internal Friction Peak

Separation of the peak component of the internal friction from the background component was tried using the results of the measurements for PLS-2 shown in Fig.4(b). By taking deviations from the dotted curves entered in Fig.4(b), the peak component is obtained as is shown in Fig.5, together with the corresponding change in the elastic stiffness.

The mechanism responsible for the internal friction peak may be simulated by a linear spring-dashpot model shown in Fig.6. In this model, the stored elastic energy can be released partly through the motion of the dashpot, which represents the viscous property of the grain boundary phase. Using this model, calculation was made for the temperature dependences of the internal friction and elastic stiffness in the peak component. In Fig.5, the results are compared with the experimental data. In this calculation, it was assumed that the spring constants K and k are independent of the temperature and the temperature dependence of the dashpot constant η is given in the Arrhenius form, $\eta = \eta_0 \exp(\Delta E/RT)$. The numerical values of the constants used in the calculation are shown in Fig.6. The value of the activation energy, $\Delta E = 159$ kcal/mol, is the value determined in the next subsection. The calculated curves show a fairly good fit to the experimental data. The discrepancy between the calculated and experimental curves may be partly due to the temperature gradient along the test section in the experiment, but a better fit may be expected by replacing the simple Maxwell model composed of the spring k and the dashpot η by the model with a distributed relaxation time spectrum taking account of the inhomogeneity in the grain boundary phase and the complicated geometry of the composite structure.

Activation Energy of the Grain Boundary Phase Viscosity

The temperature dependence of the viscosity of the grain boundary phase may be given in the Arrhenius form. In a linear visco-elastic system governed by dissipative mechanisms of the Arrhenius type with a common activation energy, if the temperature dependences of the constants of the elastic elements are negligible, the internal friction and elastic stiffness at two different frequencies plotted against the reciprocal of the absolute temperature, $1/T$, will exhibit respectively identical shapes and can be superimposed by shifting relatively along the $1/T$ axis by

$$\Delta(1/T) = R \log_e(\omega_1/\omega_2)/\Delta E \quad (1)$$

where ω_1 and ω_2 are two different frequencies. In Fig.7, the internal friction data obtained with the ultrasonic method and the torsion pendulum method are plotted against $1/T$. The most reliable method is to use the internal friction peak and, further, the corresponding elastic stiffness change in Fig.7, but, since the ultrasonic data are limited to the beginning part of the rise, plotting of the torsion pendulum data is also limited to the corresponding part. The curves for the ultrasonic and torsion pendulum data have a fairly similar shape, and the activation energies are obtained by using Eq.(1) as shown in Table II.

Table II Activation energies of the viscosity
 of the grain boundary phase

HPS	218 kcal/mol	PLS-2	159 kcal/mol
PLS-1	203 kcal/mol	PLS-3	149 kcal/mol

In general, the dynamic elastic stiffness and internal friction become strain amplitude dependent at large strain amplitudes. In the above procedure, however,

the torsion pendulum data are compared in terms of the effect of the frequency with the ultrasonic data obtained at very small strain amplitudes, and, therefore, the torsion pendulum data obtained at small strain amplitudes where the strain amplitude dependences do not appear are required. The present torsion pendulum data satisfy this condition as described previously in the subsection "Torsion Pendulum Measurements". In order to make sure, it is desirable to add the data obtained in 1 kHz range to the present data obtained in two extreme frequency ranges. In Ref.(1), the activation energies ranging 152 to 170 kcal/mol and 144 to 180 kcal/mol were reported respectively for the hot-press sintered silicon nitrides HS-110 and HS-130 of the Norton Company.

Effect of Additive Composition

Both HPS and PLS-1 are of $\text{Si}_3\text{N}_4\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-Y}_2\text{O}_3$ type. The total amount of the additives in PLS-1 is larger than in HPS. As is seen in Fig.4(a), though the internal friction peak of PLS-1 is higher than that of HPS, the peaks appear in both materials at almost the same temperature, about 1000 °C. Figures 4(b) and (c) show the above temperature is higher by about 150 °C than the corresponding temperatures of PLS-2 and PLS-3, which are respectively of $\text{Si}_3\text{N}_4\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-MgO}$ and $\text{Si}_3\text{N}_4\text{-SrO-MgO-CeO}_2$ types. This tendency is also seen in the activation energies shown in Table II; HPS and PLS-1 have higher activation energies than PLS-2 and PLS-3.

Figure 4(d) shows RS, a reaction sintered silicon nitride, which has no grain boundary phase deriving from oxide additives, also exhibits an internal friction peak at about 1350 °C, though this temperature is very high compared with the temperatures at which the peaks appear in the materials sintered with the oxide additives. A possible qualitative interpretation is to ascribe it to the remaining unreacted silicon which has the melting point at about 1400 °C. Another interpretation may be to attribute it to the phase formed by oxidation through the pores during the measurements at elevated temperatures. Both the unreacted silicon and the pores are usually found in reaction sintered silicon nitrides.

The viscous property of the grain boundary phase is sensitive to impurity content. In the specimen materials used in the present work, however, impurities are not controlled at the same level. Therefore, the above discussion should be taken on a qualitative basis.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work was supported financially by the Grant-in-Aid for Scientific Research from the Ministry of Education, Science and Culture.

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Fig.1 Set-up of ultrasonic measurement system.
(Differential path method)

Fig.3 Specimens for torsion pendulum measurements
(upper: type 1 specimen)
(lower: type 2 specimen)

Fig.2 Results of ultrasonic measurements. Changes in elastic stiffness and internal friction are shown respectively by changes in velocity and decrement of ultrasonic wave. (Shear wave. Frequency: 9.0, 6.0, 9.9, 5.4 and 6.1 MHz for HPS, PLS-1, PLS-2, PLS-3 and RS, respectively)

(a) HPS: 1.88 Hz at 15 °C, type 1 specimen with a square section 3 mm in side length. PLS-1: 1.91 Hz at 15 °C, type 2 specimen with a square section 2.8 mm in side length.

(b) PLS-2: 1.51 Hz at 15 °C, type 1 specimen with a circular section 3 mm in diameter.

Fig.4 Results of torsion pendulum measurements.
(Continued on the next page, where a detailed caption is given.)

(c) PLS-3: 1.75 Hz at 15 °C, type 2 specimen with a circular section 3 mm in diameter.

(d) RS: 1.31 Hz at 15 °C, type 1 specimen with a circular section 3 mm in diameter.

Fig.4 Results of torsion pendulum measurements. Changes in elastic stiffness and internal friction are shown respectively by changes in frequency and decrement of free oscillation.
(Continued from the previous page.)

Fig.5 Peak component of internal friction and corresponding change in elastic stiffness. PLS-2

$$k/(K+k) = 0.08$$

$$\eta = \eta_0 \exp(\Delta E/RT)$$

$$\Delta E = 159 \text{ kcal/mol}$$

$$(\eta/k)\omega = 1.0 \text{ at } 1133 \text{ } ^\circ\text{K}$$

Fig.6 Model for peak component of internal friction. Numerical values are used in calculation for PLS-2.

Fig.7 Internal friction data from Figs.2 and 4 plotted against $1/T$. (U): ultrasonic data. (T): torsion pendulum data.